

The Chemical Examination of *Solanum Xanthocarpum*, Schard and Wendle. Part I. The Constituents of the Oil from the Seeds.

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Solanum xanthocarpum (N. O. *Solanaceæ*) commonly known as Bhatkatya in Hindi and Kanta-Kari in Sanskrit and in Bengali is common throughout India. The description of the plant and its medicinal properties are given in detail in Dymock ("Pharmacographica Indica," 1891, II, 557) and Basu and Kirtikar ("Indian Medicinal plants," 1918, II, 896). The plant is of great importance in Hindu medicine, as being useful in fever, cough, asthma, constiveness, heart disease, toothache, etc.

So far scarcely any work of a chemical nature has been done on the fruits and the present investigation was undertaken to put the fruits to a thorough chemical examination. The benzene extract of the seeds yielded an oil of greenish yellow colour and some crystalline matter. The purification and constitution of the crystalline matter is being investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Fresh fruits (33.15 kg.) were dried, crushed and the pericarp separated mechanically. The dry seeds constituted 20.71%, and the pericarp 4.62% and the moisture 74.67% of the fresh fruits by weight. The ash of the crushed fruit contained 44.38% of water-soluble and 55.62% of water-insoluble inorganic material, and contained the following positive and negative radicals: potassium, iron, calcium, (in traces), magnesium, silica, carbonate, chloride, sulphate and phosphate.

Crushed seeds (30 g.) were successively extracted with various solvents in a Soxhlet's apparatus and the extracts were dried at 100° when the following results were obtained.

Benzene extract (19.28%).—The extract was a greenish yellow oil which deposited some crystalline matter on standing.

Chloroform extract (3.2%).—The extract was of yellowish brown colour and gave positive tests for alkaloids, soluble in acids, and also in caustic soda with yellow colour, forming neutral as well as basic lead salts and giving no colour with ferric chloride.

The Ethyl acetate extract (1.65%), *the acetone* (1.62%) as well as *the alcoholic extracts* (3.39%) were of yellowish brown colour, and showed the same reactions as the chloroform extract and were very slightly bitter in taste.

Extraction of the Oil.—Powdered seeds (2.2 kg.) were exhaustively extracted with benzene when 418 g. of a greenish yellow oil having characteristic odour were obtained. The crude oil was purified with animal charcoal and Fuller's earth. The oil was of bright yellow colour when viewed in thin layers and greenish yellow in thick layers.

Examination of the Oil.—The oil does not contain nitrogen or sulphur. It burns with slightly smoky flame and is slightly optically active showing a rotation of $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -1.35$ in chloroform. On examination it was found to be semi-drying; $d_{27}^{20} = 0.9240$; it does not solidify upto -11° but becomes thick; acid value, 70.78; acetyl value, 40.4; saponification value, 182.5; Hehner's value, 94.9; iodine value, 124.3; unsaponifiable matter, 1.2%.

150 G. of the oil were saponified in the usual manner with alcoholic potash and the unsaponifiable matter extracted with ether. The fatty acids were then extracted in the usual manner. The mixed fatty acids have the following constants: Consistency, liquid; $d_{27}^{20} = 0.8775$; neutralisation value, 173.9; mean M.W., 322.7; iodine value, 121.37.

The mixture of the fatty acids (52 g.) was then separated into saturated (solid) and unsaturated (liquid) acids by the Twitchell's lead salt alcohol method (*J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806). During the separation of saturated and unsaturated acids, a small quantity of resinous acid insoluble in ether also separated and it is to their presence that the mean molecular weight of the mixed acids is so high. Table I gives the percentage, iodine value and the mean molecular weight of the saturated and unsaturated acids.

TABLE I.

Acids.	In mixed acids.	In the oil.	Iodine value.	Mean M. W.
Saturated	16.62%	15.77%	4.24	285
Unsaturated	83.38	79.11	129.7	279.8

Examination of Unsaturated Acids.—The unsaturated acids, separated by the above method, showed beautiful green fluorescence, and their constituents were determined quantitatively by the method of Jmaieson and Baughman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1197) by preparing their bromine addition products. The hexabromo derivative of linolenic acid is insoluble in cold ether; since no precipitate insoluble in ether was formed, the absence of linolenic acid was confirmed. The ether-soluble portion was dissolved in petroleum ether and cooled when crystals of linolic tetrabromide (m.p. 113-14°) were separated showing the presence of linolic acid. The residue was evaporated to dryness and the bromine content estimated. Table II contains the results of the analysis of the bromine addition products.

TABLE II.

Weight of unsaturated acids taken	5.6192 g.
Linolic tetrabromide (insoluble in petroleum ether)	2.8294
Residue (dibromide and tetrabromide)	7.1552
Bromine content of the residue	42.33%
Dibromo-oleic acid in residue	64.1% or 4.7800 g.
Tetrabromolinolic acid in residue	35.9% or 2.6770 g.
Total tetrabromide found	5.5064 g.
Linolic acid equivalent to tetrabromide	45.74% or 2.5700 g.
Oleic acid equivalent to dibromide	54.26% or 3.0490 g.

The proportions of the linolic and oleic acids in the unsaturated acids was also determined from the iodine value of the liquid acids.

Table III (a) contains the percentage of the linolic and oleic acids in the unsaturated acids, and the percentage of their glycerides in

original oil calculated by bromine addition method, and Table III (b) percentages calculated by iodine method.

TABLE III (a)

Acid.	Found by bromine addition products.	In the total fatty acids.	In the original oil.
Oleic acid	54.26%	45.23%	42.93%
Linolic acid	45.74	38.14	36.19

TABLE III (b)

Acids.	Calculated by iodine value.	In the total fatty acids.	In the original oil.
Oleic	56.38%	47.00	46.71
Linolic	43.62	36.40	34.55

The theoretical iodine value of a mixture consisting of 54.26% of oleic acid and 45.74% of linolic acid is 131.7, which agrees fairly well with the observed iodine value of the unsaturated acids (129.7).

Examination of the Saturated Acids.—The saturated acids separated by the lead salt alcohol method were freed from traces of liquid acids by pressing over porous plate. The acids, thus obtained, were perfectly solid, slightly yellowish white in colour, m. p. 52°-56°.

The mixture of the saturated acids was converted into the methyl ester (10 g.) and fractionally distilled under reduced pressure. The iodine values and the saponification values of the different fractions were determined and the mean molecular weight calculated. The M. W. of the methyl palmitate is 270.3 and that of methyl stearate 298.4. The M. W. of the three fractions lies between these two values and indicates a mixture of the two. The M. W. of the last fraction is greater than 298 and hence contains the ester of an acid of greater M. W. than stearate and probably arachidate. The percentages of the acids were determined in the different fractions by means of these mean M. W. and the iodine value (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 152).

Table IV contains the result of the fraction and Table V the results of analysis.

TABLE IV.

Fraction.	B. p.	Weight of the fraction.	Acids.	In the saturated acids.	In the original oil.
1	200-210/1.2 mm.	1.6800 g.	Palmitic	34.07 %	5.37 %
2	278-80/0.7 mm.	3.2378	Stearic	61.93	9.77
3	280-81/0.7 m.m.	2.7174	Arachidic (?)	2.20	0.35
4	Residue	2.0420	Unsaturated	1.79	0.28

TABLE VI.

Fraction.	Iodine number.	Spanification value.	Mean M. W.	Unsaturated.	Mean M. W. of esters of saturated acids.
1	2.76	203.45	75.9	0.357 g. (2.12%)	275.5
2	1.69	197.74	287.2	0.423 (1.30%)	283.7
3	1.21	190.0	295.3	0.232 (0.85%)	295.3
4	4.40	186.40	301.0	0.633 (0.31%)	301.4

TABLE V.

TABLE V (contd.).

Fraction.	Palmitic acid.	Stearic acid.	Arachidic acid.
1	1.2700 g. (75.53%)	0.2898 g. (17.25%)	...
2	1.5830 (48.9%)	1.4510 (44.82%)	...
3	0.2815 (10.36%)	2.2810 (83.93%)	...
4	...	1.6760 (82.10%)	0.2020 g. (9.89%)

Examination of the Unsaponifiable Matter.—The unsaponifiable matter obtained by ether extraction of the soap was washed in ethereal solution repeatedly with water. The dried ethereal solution was distilled when a yellowish white amorphous matter was obtained.

It was repeatedly crystallised from minimum quantity of alcohol, and thus two sets of perfectly white flakes were obtained with different melting points, and thus proving that the unsaponifiable matter is a mixture of two sterols in addition to some sticky yellow colouring matter which is practically insoluble in cold alcohol. On recrystallising from alcohol twice, the first crop melted completely at 122° with previous shrinking at 92° , and the second at $142-43^{\circ}$ but without any sign of shrinkage before melting. They gave the various colour reactions of the sterol and were optically active, $[\alpha]_D^{32} = +16.24$ in chloroform ($c, 1.2930$). The sample, crystallised from chloroform and air-dried, was analysed. [Found: C, 75.5; H, 11.1. $C_{24}H_{44}O_3$ (?) requires C, 75.8; H, 11.6 per cent]. The other sample showed $[\alpha]_D^{32} = -83.45$ (?) in chloroform ($c, 0.6890$); the substance, crystallised from alcohol and air-dried, was analysed. (Found: C, 83.12, 83.41; H, 11.42, 11.66. $C_{25}H_{42}O$ requires C, 83.8; H, 11.7; while $C_{26}H_{44}O$ requires C, 83.8; H, 11.8 per cent).

SUMMARY.

The examination of the oil showed the presence of the following substances: - Oleic acid (42.93%); linolic acid (36.18%); palmitic acid (5.37%); stearic acid (9.77%); arachidic acid (?) (0.35%); and unsaponifiable matter (a mixture of two sterols, 1.2%).

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